

A CASE STUDY ON ROLE OF UTTARABASTI OF TUBONIL OIL IN THE REMOVAL OF B/L TUBAL BLOCKAGE

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ABSTRACT

The large number of global female population experiencing infertility, with a significant percentage of those having tubal factor infertility. According to medical science the tubal obstruction is one of the main causes of female infertility. Ayurveda suggested *Uttar Basti* as an important therapeutic option for such types of condition. *Uttar Basti*, an intrauterine therapeutic instillation used in Ayurveda that aims to clear blockages in the fallopian tubes and restore reproductive function. In present case study Ayurvedic therapeutic method was evaluated to determine its efficacy in treating tubal blockages. Tubonil oil was used to administer *Uttar basti* due to its *Vata-Kapha Shamana* and *Lekhana* properties. *Uttar basti* was administered at a dosage of 2-3 ml. After the completion of therapy, patient had stopped menstruating and completed all screening testing. Positive outcomes were shown in this case study since patient demonstrated partial recovery of tubal patency following *Uttar Basti* therapy. Study confirms that *Uttar basti* is an effective, safe method of treating tubal blockage.

KEYWORDS: *Ayurveda, Uttar Basti, Tubonil oil, Fallopian tubes, Infertility.*

INTRODUCTION

Tubal obstruction can impede the movement of the sperm or egg from reaching the site of fertilization and ultimately prevent natural conception. There are many

causes of fallopian tube blockage as depicted in **Figure 1**. The typical treatment for tubal blockages has been through the use of tubal reconstructive surgery.^[1-3]

Figure 1: Major Causes of Fallopian Tube Blockage.

In Ayurveda, infertility is viewed as a consequence of disturbances in *Dosha* and obstruction of *Srotas*.

According to Ayurveda four components of conception such as; *Ritu, Kshetra, Ambu* and *Beeja* are dependent on

the health of the *Artavavaha Srotas*, which refers to the health of the reproductive system through the mobility and viability of the eggs and sperm. The obstruction of the *Artavavaha Srotas* is equivalent to the blockage of the fallopian tubes.^[3-5]

According to Ayurvedic principles, tubal blockages occur primarily as a result of the vitiation of *Vata* and *Kapha Doshas*. *Kapha* causes *Sanga* through its *Guru* and *Picchila* qualities, while aggravated *Vata* will cause functional impairment and *Samkocha*. The Process of Pathology involves the *Sthanasamshraya* of vitiated *Doshas* within the *Artava Bija Vah Srotas* (fallopian tubes) resulting in *Shopha*, *Paka* and *Sanga sroto dushti* leading to *Garbhahaya Nalika Avarodha*.

In Ayurveda *Uttar Basti* is indicated for disorders of the reproductive tract. In this therapy medicated oils/decoctions are instilled into the uterus through the vagina; thus removing obstruction, pacifying vitiated *Doshas* and correcting the normal patency of the tubes. *Uttar Basti* is thought to have *Snehana*, *Shothahra* and

Ashta Vidha Pariksha

Nadi	Mala	Mutra	Jivha	Shabda	Sparsha	Druk	Akruti
76/min	Regular	6–8 times/day	Prakruta	Prakruta	Prakruta	Prakruta	Prakruta

General Examination

The patient was moderately built, there was no oedema, her blood pressure was found to be 130/80 mmHg, her

Systemic Examination

- ✓ Respiratory system: Normal vesicular breath sounds
- ✓ Central nervous system: Conscious and oriented
- ✓ Cardiovascular system: S₁ and S₂ heard normally
- ✓ Per speculum: Cervix and vagina appeared normal

TREATMENT PROTOCOL

✓ Formulation (Tubonil Oil)

Tubonil Oil is an ayurvedic proprietary herbal preparation used for the treatment of gynecologic problems such as tubal obstruction, polycystic ovarian disease and infertility in addition to being an essential product to maintain women's reproductive health. Tubonil oil is primarily for female reproductive health and is often used in conjunction with other therapies to help women with issues involving blocked or abnormal reproductive pathways. The formulation consists of *Kshar Taila*, *Kasisadi Taila*, *Apamarg Beej Siddha Taila* and *Tila Taila*.

✓ Administration of Formulation

2 to 3 ml for *Uttar Basti* i.e. Intrauterine administration. In the menstrual cycle, *Uttar Basti* was given, following *Abhyanga* and *Swedana*. With the patient's informed agreement, *Uttar Basti* was carried out for few days in a row following the end of the menstrual cycle.

Lekhana effects on function so as to restore normal function of reproduction. Considering this fact present case report demonstrated role of *Uttarabasti* of tubonil oil in the removal of B/L Tubal Blockage.^[4-6]

CASE REPORT

A woman of 32 years old came with the main complaint of not being able to conceive. She reported unsuccessful attempts at intrauterine insemination throughout the previous six months, and she had been married for 06 years. She reported no history of other chronic or metabolic illnesses. Systemic examination showed no significant abnormalities, her menstrual cycle, which lasted three to four days and had a relatively substantial flow, was regular.

Personal History

The patient had a healthy appetite and ate a vegetarian diet; there was a disruption in sleep. Clear and regular bowel movements were observed and micturition was also found to be normal.

respiration rate was observed 22/min and her pulse rate was found to be 76/min.

Poorvakarma

Prior to the procedure, both instruments and oils underwent autoclaving to be properly sterilized. The lower abdomen, back and lower limbs were treated with *Snehana*, followed by *Nadi Swedana*.

Pradhan Karma

During the primary procedure, the participant was positioned in dorsal lithotomy and after thoroughly cleaning the shaved perineal region with antiseptic solution her vagina and cervix were inspected using Cusco's speculum with the uterus sounded for depth. In a head-low position, *Uttar Basti* cannula was slowly introduced through syringe into the uterus.

Pashchat Karma

The patient was kept head-low for two hours following administration. A hot water bag was used to gently fomentate the lower abdomen. During the course of treatment, she was instructed to refrain from coitus and to avoid eating anything extremely hot.

FOLLOW UP AND RESULT

Throughout the *Basti* operations, the patient was closely monitored and reassessed every 15 days. Her overall health showed signs of improvement within a month. A viable intrauterine pregnancy was confirmed by ultrasound few weeks later, which showed a single, well-defined gestational sac with positive fetal heart activity. The tubal function had been restored, as evidenced by bilateral tubal patency and free peritoneal leakage.

DISCUSSION

The purpose of Tubonil oil is to assist with resolution of blockages of the fallopian tubes. The formulation contains active ingredients with *Kshara*, which are believed to allow the obstruction to get resolve, clinical observations have shown a high degree of success after the use of Tubonil oil; therefore, this is an excellent adjunct to tubal obstruction treatment. Ayurvedic principles refer to a tubal obstruction as an example of *Strotas Dushti* due to *Kapha* and *Vata Dosha* vitiation.^[6-8] *Lekhana Karma* is essential to alleviates *Kapha* and *Meda* vitiation along with *Vata* predominance and *Ushna Guna Yukta Basti* helps to achieve this goal. The applied *Taila* produce a *Lekhana* effect due to the presence of *Kshara*. Oil alleviates *Kapha* and *Meda Dushti*, through its *Ushna* qualities and restored *Dosha* balance. *Uttar Basti* offers *Vata-Kapha Shamana* effects which support normal reproduction process. *Tridoashghna*, *Tikshna*, *Ushna*, *Sukshma* and *Lekhana* effects of employed therapy helped greatly to clearing tubal blockages.^[8-10]

CONCLUSION

The patient conceived within few months of receiving Ayurvedic therapy, she successfully finished her gestational period without experiencing any significant difficulties. This single case study produces notable outcomes, with little invasiveness and reduced expenses. Therefore, more systematic clinical evaluation of this therapy procedure is warranted as it may be a promising option for addressing infertility caused by tubal obstruction.

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